

Intellectual Property Rights: An Overview

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Introduction:

Intellectual property (IP) is a term referring to creation of the intellect (the term used in studies of the human mind) for which a monopoly (from Greek word monos means single poleis to sell) is assigned to designated owners by law. Intellectual property rights are like any other property right. Intellectual Property Rights are themselves a form of property called intangible property. Property designates those things that are commonly recognized as being the possessions of an individual or a group. A right of ownership is associated with property that establishes the good as being "one's own thing" in relation to other individuals or groups, assuring the owner the right to dispense with the property in a manner he or she deems fit, whether to use or not use, exclude others from using, or to transfer ownership.

Properties are of two types - tangible property and intangible property i.e. one that is physically present and the other which is not in any physical form. Building, land, house, cash, jewellery are few examples of tangible properties which can be seen and felt physically. On the other hand there is a kind of valuable property that cannot be felt physically as it does not have a physical form. Intellectual property is one of the forms of intangible property which commands a material value which can also be higher than the value of a tangible asset or property. Legal rights conferred on such property are called Intellectual property rights.

Intellectual Property Rights allow creators, or owners, of patents, trademarks or copyrighted works to benefit from their own work or investment in a creation. These rights are outlined in Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which provides for the right to benefit from the protection of moral and material interests resulting from authorship of scientific, literary or artistic productions. The importance of intellectual property was first recognized in the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (1883) and the Berne Convention for the Protection of Literary and Artistic Works (1886). Both treaties are administered by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO).

There are different types of Intellectual Property Rights as follow:

- Patents
- Trademarks
- Industrial designs
- Geographical indications of goods
- Copyrights
- Protection of Integrated Circuits layout design

- Biological diversity
- Plant varieties and farmers rights
- Undisclosed information

Intellectual property is divided into two categories: Industrial Property and Copyright. Industrial Property includes patents for inventions, trademarks, industrial designs and geographical indications. Copyright covers literary works (such as novels, poems and plays), films, music, artistic works (e.g., drawings, paintings, photographs and sculptures) and architectural design.

A. Industrial Property:

Industrial Property covers patents for inventions, trademarks, industrial designs and geographical indications. Simply stated, inventions are new solutions to technical problems and industrial designs are aesthetic creations determining the appearance of industrial products. In addition, industrial property includes trademarks, service marks, commercial names and designations, including indications of source and appellations of origin, and protection against unfair competition.

Patents:

A Patent is an exclusive rights granted for an invention – a product or process that provides a new way of doing something, or that offers a new technical solution to a problem. A patent provides patent owners with protection for their inventions. Protection is granted for a limited period, generally 20 years. Patents provide incentives to individuals by recognizing their creativity and offering the possibility of material reward for their marketable inventions. These incentives encourage innovation, which in turn enhances the quality of human life.

There are three types of patents:

- i. Utility patents may be granted to anyone who invents or discovers any new and useful process, machine, article of manufacture, or composition of matter, or any new and useful improvement thereof;
- ii. Design patents may be granted to anyone who invents a new, original, and ornamental design for an article of manufacture; and
- iii. Plant patents may be granted to anyone who invents or discovers and asexually reproduces any distinct and new variety of plant.

Trademarks:

A trademark or service mark is a word, name, symbol, or device used to indicate the source, quality and ownership of a product or service. A trademark is used in the marketing is recognizable sign, design or expression which identifies products or service of a particular source from those of others. The trademark owner can be an individual, business organization, or any legal entity. A trademark may be located on a package, a label, a voucher or on the product itself. For the sake of corporate identity trademarks are also being.

Industrial Designs:

Industrial Designs are the features of shape, configuration, pattern, ornament or composition of lines or colours applied to the product which makes it look different from other articles in the market. The design must be new and distinct. The design protection is provided for 10 years. The period of protection is extendable to 5 years after the expiry of 10 years' duration.

Geographical Indications:

Geographical indications of goods are defined as that aspect of industrial property which refers to the geographical indication referring to a country or to a place situated therein as being the country. Geographical Indication is primarily an agricultural, natural or a manufactured product (handicrafts and industrial goods) originating from a definite geographical territory. Solapur Chaddar, Basmati Rice, Darjeeling Tea, Kanchipuram Silk Saree, Nagpur Orange and Ratnagiri Hapus are examples of geographical indications.

B. Copyright and Related Rights:

The term "copyright" is not defined under the Indian Copyright Act, 1957 (hereinafter referred to as "Copyright Act"). The general connotation of the term copyright refers to the "right to copy" which is available only to the author or the creator, as the case may be. Thus, any other person who copies the original work would be amount to infringement under the Copyright Act. Copyright ensures certain minimum safeguards of the rights of authors over their creations.

Copyright is a right given by the law to creators of literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works and producers of cinematograph films and sound recordings. Copyright relates to literary and artistic creations, such as books, music, paintings and sculptures, films and technology-based works such as computer programs and electronic databases. Copyright is also known as authors' rights. The expression authors' rights refers to the creator of an artistic work, its author, thus underlining that, as recognized in most laws, authors have certain specific rights in their creations that only they can exercise, which are often referred to as moral rights, such as the right to prevent distorted reproductions of the work. Other rights, such as the right to make copies, can be exercised by third parties with the author's permission, for example, by a publisher who obtains a license to this effect from the author.

Moral and Economic Rights:

Copyright protects the expression of a person's ideas. The expression must be "original," which, in this context, means a work that is not a copy of another work. The ideas in the work do not need to be original, but the form of expression must be an original creation by the author. It also protects the creators and their heirs and successors (generally referred to as "right holders"). The right holder(s) of a work can authorize or prohibit:

- its reproduction in all forms, including print form and sound recording;
- its public performance and communication to the public;
- its broadcasting;

- its translation into other languages; and
- its adaptation, such as from a novel to a screenplay for a film.

Many types of works protected under the laws of copyright and related rights require mass distribution, communication and financial investment for their successful dissemination (for example, publications, sound recordings and films). Hence, creators often transfer these rights to companies better able to develop and market the works, in return for compensation in the form of payments and/or royalties (compensation based on a percentage of revenues generated by the work).

Benefits of Copyright:

Copyright and related rights protection is an essential component in fostering human creativity and innovation. Giving authors, artists and creators incentives in the form of recognition and fair economic reward increases their activity and output and can also enhance the results. By ensuring the existence and enforceability of rights, individuals and companies can more easily invest in the creation, development and global dissemination of their works. It helps to increase access to and enhance the enjoyment of culture, knowledge and entertainment the world over and also stimulates economic and social development.

Copyright Board:

There are no special courts for the purpose of dealing with copyright cases. The regular courts try these cases which basically lack knowledge and expertise in the field of copyright. There is a Copyright Board to adjudicate certain cases pertaining to copyright. The government has set up a Copyright Enforcement Advisory Council (CEAC) to adjudicate certain matters relating to copyright.

Conclusion:

Countries have laws to protect intellectual property for two main reasons. One is to give statutory expression to the moral and economic rights of creators in their creations and the rights of the public in access to those creations. The second is to promote creativity and the dissemination and application of its results and to encourage fair trading which would contribute to economic and social development. Intellectual property rights aims at safeguarding creators and other producers of intellectual goods and services by granting them certain time-limited rights to control the use made of those productions.

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